

IMPACTS OF SHORT ADS VIDEOS ON FACEBOOK ON THE YOUNG USERS' PURCHASE INTENTIONS - RESULTS

KHOA QUOC BUI

MA, DBA, Swiss Institute of Management and Innovation (SIMI), Switzerland. Email : khoa_bq@yahoo.com

YEN NGUYEN THI HOANG

MBA, Faculty of Marketing - International Business, HUTECH University, Vietnam.
Email : nth.yen83@hutech.edu.vn

HONG THI CUC NGUYEN

PhD, Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics and Finance, Vietnam. Email : hongntc@uef.edu.vn

TOAI VAN NGUYEN

MBA, PhD Student, Ho Chi Minh University of Industry and Trade, Vietnam. Email:nv.toai0609@gmail.com

TRUNG NGUYEN QUANG

PhD, Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics and Finance, Vietnam.

Abstract

The development of short advertising videos has become a popular strategy for businesses in their operations, especially when the content of these short advertising videos primarily targets young user groups. This demonstrates the necessity of focusing research on analyzing the impact of short advertising videos on Facebook on the purchase intentions of the young user group. The aim of this study was achieved through the use of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, with data collected from 257 randomly selected college students from 5 private universities, representing young users. The analysis results showed that purchase intentions are influenced by 4 factors, with (1) Usefulness being the most impactful, followed by (2) Promotion, (3) Entertainment, and the least influential being (4) Interactivity. This study not only contributes to academic research but also assists businesses in effectively leveraging the potential of advertising videos on Facebook.

Keywords: Facebook, Young Users, Short Advertising Videos, Purchasing Intentions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of advertising videos on Facebook for young users is becoming an undeniable trend. Nowadays, videos have become a powerful, engaging, and effective medium to reach young audiences on the most popular social media platform in the world - Facebook. The use of advertising videos on Facebook not only attracts user attention but also creates positive interaction, offering unique opportunities and effective methods for businesses to connect with customers (Donmez, 2022), especially young customers.

The visual and auditory impact of videos particularly helps to capture and retain the attention of young viewers. Additionally, the ease of sharing on social media platforms helps videos spread rapidly, providing opportunities to reach diverse customer groups and exert significant influence on young users, opening up creative space and great potential for marketing and brand promotion in today's increasingly competitive market.

Specifically, the trend of short advertising videos being broadcasted on various diverse media platforms, suitable for viewing on mobile devices and any internet-connected tool. The flexibility of these videos, coupled with creatively crafted content within a few minutes, can lead to highly effective social media dissemination (Han, 2022). In today's digital age, online shopping behavior on social media platforms, especially Facebook, has become common and significantly influences users' purchasing intentions on social media. In Vietnam, as of September 2022, there are over 80 million Facebook users, accounting for about 80% of the country's population (according to statistics from bocongthuong.com.vn). With such a high number of Facebook users, the potential for reaching users with short advertising videos is promising, and live streaming on Facebook can help businesses reach a wider audience as it can be easily shared and accessed through social media platforms (Skjuve & Brandtzaeg, 2019).

The objective of this paper is to study the factors influencing users' purchase intentions from short advertising videos on Facebook, not only to gain a better understanding of online shopping behavior but also to establish a foundation for building effective short advertising video strategies based on social media. From these factors, the authors further contribute important managerial implications for businesses to leverage the most positive impact of short advertising video dissemination on users' purchase intentions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Online advertisement

According to Seo & Park (2018), social media is clearly defined as a program or online application platform that reduces interactions, collaborative work, or content sharing, especially in marketing activities. Currently, there are numerous social media marketing platforms such as TikTok, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, WeChat, Snapchat, Pinterest, Quora, and others. These platforms provide marketers with a wide range of options for marketing their products, including business data, customer groups, or different advertising messages.

When marketers advertise on social media platforms like Facebook, they usually leverage the internet's maximum dissemination and connection to promote advertisers' information, products, services, and ideas to the audience (Suharyanto & Hidayat, 2018). However, advertising information is not always readily accepted by customers, as the attitude of social media users plays a crucial role in evaluating the effectiveness of any online advertising campaign (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

2.2 Online short advertising videos and purchase intention

According to Hu TAO & Jing-hui YANG (2018), short videos are video content lasting only a few seconds, suitable for viewing and entertainment on new media platforms. With the widespread and diverse social media platforms and mobile applications, young users have multiple ways to access information through videos, making short advertising videos a trend that enables them to access more information. Short advertising videos often

focus on quickly and interestingly conveying the main message, attracting viewers' attention in a short time. This reflects the short-term attention span of young users and their desire to consume information quickly and easily. Therefore, for businesses, utilizing short advertising videos to reach users to enhance brand awareness and promote customer loyalty (Wen-sheng, 2015) is an extremely important strategy. Businesses can cleverly combine images, music, text, and viewer psychology in short advertising videos to influence consumer behavior on social media platforms such as TikTok (Kurdi et al., 2022) and Facebook, thereby effectively stimulating purchase intention and encouraging young users' shopping actions.

However, research by Voorveld (2019) also indicates that when the same advertisement is displayed multiple times, viewers may feel uncomfortable and associate the advertisement with the brand providing the service. This is something that businesses need to consider in their advertising strategies.

2.3 Online Purchase Intention Theories

Online shopping on social media platforms is becoming increasingly popular with modern consumers. This business model allows consumers to search for and purchase products directly from sellers through social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Pinterest. Using social media for shopping provides convenience and creates a more interactive shopping experience for consumers, significantly influencing their purchase intentions. According to Donni, Dastane, Haba, & Selvaraj (2018), purchase intentions are greatly influenced by customers' online searches and the time spent browsing e-commerce websites. Additionally, when shopping on social media, consumers can see reviews from other buyers, interact directly with sellers, and even participate in online shopping communities to share experiences. Furthermore, providing detailed information about products through photos, videos, and advertising posts also helps consumers understand the products better before making a purchase decision. In summary, as Athapaththu & Kulathunga (2018) suggest, forming an online purchase intention involves going through various stages of purchase intention before completing the product evaluation based on experience, current knowledge, preferences, persuasive factors, and the influence of other consumers' purchasing decisions.

However, shopping on social media also presents challenges related to transaction safety and security. Being aware of the seller's authenticity, product risks, financial risks, security risks, and privacy risks significantly influence consumers' purchase intentions (Tran, 2020).

2.4 Related studies

Martins et al., (2019) research model yielded results after surveying 303 young users in Portugal, concluding that consumers find advertising on smartphones to be trustworthy, interesting, a good source of information for purchasing products, and providing opportunities for rewards. Flow experience was positively influenced by credibility,

entertainment value, incentives, and advertising value, while information relevance and stimulation hurt the flow experience before affecting purchase intention.

This can be clearly illustrated through the following model::

Figure 1: Research model of Martins et al., (2019) (Source: Martins et al., 2019)

Rajan, P., Lyn, F., Mun, N., Sian, K., & Yi, L. (2021) have developed a model based on 2 models inherited and analyzed the use of social media and the satisfaction of university students in the study by Kircaburun et al.,(2020). Their study resulted in factors of Usefulness, Informativeness, Entertainment, Time, and Convenience positively influencing the online purchase intentions of university students based on Facebook advertising through a survey of 310 non-graduated university students from a university in Malaysia.

Figure 2: Research model of Pragash et al., (2021)

(Source: Pragash et al., 2021)

The research model by Ngo et al., (2022) focuses on evaluating the influence of advertising on TikTok on the online purchase intentions of Generation Z in Ho Chi Minh City. This study collected data from 250 individuals born between 1995 and 2010 and then conducted exploratory factor analysis and SEM modeling. The results indicated that there are 4 significant factors of TikTok advertising influencing the online purchase intentions of Gen Z, including informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and interaction. All four factors positively impact online purchase intentions, with informational content being the most influential.

Figure 3: Research model of Ngo et al., (2022)

(Source: Ngo et al., 2022)

3. HYPOTHESES AND RESEARCH MODEL

- Inheriting the research model of Martins et al., (2019), the author selected the factors: ***Informativeness, Credibility, Entertainment, and Promotion.***
- Inheriting the research model of Pragash et al., (2021), the author selected the factors: ***Informativeness, Entertainment, and Usefulness.***

- Inheriting the research model of Ngo et al., (2022), the author selected the factors: **Informativeness, Entertainment, Credibility, and Interactivity.**

Table 1: Selective factors of the proposed model

Reference models	Martins et al., (2019)	Pragash et al., (2021)	Ngo et al., (2022)	Conceptual model
Informativeness	X	X	X	X
Entertainment	X	X	X	X
Credibility	X		X	X
Interactivity			X	X
Promotion	X			X
Usefulness		X		X

Based on the synthesis of studies on the purchase intentions of young users mentioned above, the author proposes a research model that includes the following factors:

- 1) Informativeness
- 2) Entertainment
- 3) Credibility
- 4) Interactivity
- 5) Promotion
- 6) Usefulness

Figure 4: Conceptual model

The model is constructed with the following hypotheses:

- **Hypothesis H1: Informativeness (INF)** is positively related (+) to the purchase intention of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos.
- **Hypothesis H2: Entertainment (ENT)** is positively related (+) to the purchase intention of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos.
- **Hypothesis H3: Credibility (CRE)** is positively related (+) to the purchase intention of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos.
- **Hypothesis H4: Interactivity (INT)** is positively related (+) to the purchase intention of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos.
- **Hypothesis H5: Promotion (PRO)** is positively related (+) to the purchase intention of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos.
- **Hypothesis H6: Usefulness (USF)** is positively related (+) to the purchase intention of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

After completing the construction of the purchase intention model of young users on Facebook after watching short advertising videos, the author synthesized 27 proposed questions based on 6 hypotheses for 06 independent variables and 01 dependent variable. To ensure the accuracy of the results when running data on SPSS or SEM, following the recommendation of Hair et al., (2006), the author surveyed a minimum sample of 300 people. The sampling method was carried out using non-probability and convenience sampling, focusing only on responses from young people aged 18 – 25, who are students in Districts 1, 3, and Binh Thanh in Ho Chi Minh City. These individuals are aware of and intend to make online purchases on Facebook after watching short advertising videos. In total, 257 valid surveys were used to run the data, with a frequency statistic result showing that 37% were male and 63% were female respondents. Among them, 60.7% were aged 22 – 25, predominantly individuals with incomes ranging from 7 – 15 million VND (36.96%) participated in the survey. The author conducted qualitative research constructed 27 quantitative questions and then surveyed on a 5-point Likert scale to collect sufficient data. The data was then imported into SPSS 20.0 to obtain specific research results on Cronbach's alpha, EFA, and Regression, as presented in the study's results section.

5. RESULT ANALYSIS

5.1 Reliability

The table below shows detailed results regarding the reliability of Cronbach's alpha for 6 independent variables, including ***Informativeness, Entertainment, Credibility, Interactivity, Promotion, Usefulness***, and one dependent variable, which is the ***purchase intention of young Facebook users*** after watching short advertising videos.

The reliability results range from 0.778 to 0.890, which is higher than 0.6, and the corrected item-total correlation coefficients for each observed variable are greater than 0.3. In summary, all conditions have been met.

Table 2: Reliability test with Cronbach's Alpha

Factors	Observed variables				Cronbach's Alpha
	INF1	INF2	INF3	INF4	
Informativeness (INF)	0.771	0.766	0.762	0.787	0.818
	ENT1	ENT2	ENT3	ENT4	
Entertainment (ENT)	0.858	0.852	0.825	0.871	0.890
	CRE1	CRE2	CRE3	CRE4	
Credibility (CRE)	0.805	0.792	0.747	0.802	0.831
	INT1	INT2	INT3	INT4	
Interactivity (INT)	0.855	0.790	0.795	0.819	0.855
	PRO1	PRO2	PRO3	PRO4	
Promotion (PRO)	0.820	0.818	0.808	0.779	0.848
	USF1	USF2	USF3	USF4	
Usefulness (USF)	0.850	0.805	0.830	0.820	0.864
	PI1		PI2	PI3	
Purchase intention of young Facebook users (PI)	0.732		0.681	0.687	0.778

5.2 EFA analysis

In the final exploratory factor analysis (EFA), the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure yielded a value of 0.949, and the significance level (Sig.) was 0.000 in Bartlett's test, indicating the model's suitability for the data. The EFA results revealed that 22 observed variables were evenly distributed into 6 distinct clusters, with each factor group having an Eigenvalue greater than 1, suggesting that the model generated is sufficiently accurate. The total variance accounted for was 72.81%, indicating that these 6 factor groups collectively explain 72.8% of the variability in the research data. Table 3 presents the final EFA results with 6 factor groups and 22 observed variables.

Table 3: Rotation matrix results (EFA)

No	Contents	Observed variables	Factors					
			1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Entertainment (ENT)	ENT1	.827					
2		ENT2	.779					
3		ENT3	.729					
4		ENT4	.701					
5	Usefulness (USF)	USF2		.791				
6		USF4		.723				
7		USF3		.668				
8		USF1		.567				
9	Promotion (PRO)	PRO1			.710			
10		PRO2			.708			
11		PRO3			.694			
12		PRO4			.636			
13	Credibility (CRE)	CRE3				.788		

14		CRE1				.684		
15		CRE2				.555		
16		CRE4				.546		
17	Interactivity (INT)	INT4					.768	
18		INT3					.761	
19		INT2					.670	
20	Informativeness (INF)	INF2						.723
21		INF1						.636
22		INF3						.543
Eigenvalue			10.026	1.511	1.237	1.118	1.095	1.017
Variance extract (%)			49.47	55.39	60.81	65.55	69.43	72.81
Cumulative (%)								72.81
Sig.								0.000
KMO								0.944

5.3 Multiple Linear Regression analysis

After conducting regression tests against the overall dataset, the model did not violate the test hypotheses and showed statistical significance. However, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for 4 out of 6 factors was below 10, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. Specifically, after excluding 2 variables that were not significant for the purchase intention (PI) of young Facebook users, namely "Informativeness" (INF) and "Credibility" (CRE), as their Sig. values were 0.357 and 0.052 respectively, greater than 0.05, the R coefficient ultimately yielded a value of 0.824, demonstrating a strong correlation among the variables in the model. The regression results of the model indicated an R-squared value (R²) of 0.679, signifying that 67.90% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the 6 independent factors.

In Table 4, the standardized Beta coefficients will range from 0.149 to 0.387, representing the impact ratio of each independent factor on the dependent variable: ***purchase intention on Facebook***.

Table 4: Multiple Linear Regression results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std. error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
Constant	.296	.141		2.097	.037		
ENT	.196	.045	.179	3.957	.000	.519	1.625
USF	.384	.056	.387	6.859	.000	.405	1.467
PRO	.214	.053	.213	4.036	.000	.453	1.207
INT	.163	.047	.149	3.199	.002	.491	1.036
R	0,824						
R Square	0,679						
Adjusted R ²	0,674						
Durbin Watson	2.061						
F (105,490)	Sig. = 0,000						
Unstandardized Function	Purchase intention of young Facebook users = 0.296 + 0.196*ENT + 0.384*USF + 0.214*PRO + 0.163*INT						

Based on the regression results above, the results are specifically explained according to the standardized equation as follows:

Purchase intention of young Facebook users = 0.179* Informativeness + 0.387*Usefulness + 0.213*Promotion + 0.149*Interactivity.

In which, two factors "**Informativeness (INF)**" And "**Credibility (CRE)**" are eliminated, thus the two hypotheses H1 and H3 have been eliminated and the remaining 4 factors have impacts with specific levels. following form:

Table 5: Determine the importance of independent variables in percentage

No	Variables	Standard. Beta	Percent %	Level of impact
1	Entertainment (ENT)	0.179	17.90%	3
2	Interactivity (INT)	0.149	14.90%	4
3	Promotion (PRO)	0.213	21.30%	2
4	Usefulness (USF)	0.387	38.70%	1

Based on Table 5, we can observe that the "Usefulness" factor (USF) contributes 38.70%, the "Promotion" factor (PRO) contributes 21.30%, the "Entertainment" factor (ENT) contributes 17.90%, and the "Interactivity" factor (INT) contributes 14.90%. Therefore, the order of influence on the purchase intention on Facebook among HUTECH students is as follows: Usefulness (USF) is the most important factor, followed by Promotion (PRO), then Entertainment (ENT), and finally Interactivity (INT).

Figure 5: Research Model (Final)

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis results, the study has revealed the positive influence of 4 out of 6 independent factors on the purchase intention of young Facebook users after watching short advertisement videos. The correlation coefficient analysis and p-value also indicate a good model fit. The research concludes that only 4 hypotheses were accepted under specific conditions. During the reliability analysis phase using Cronbach's alpha, no observed variables were eliminated. The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) phase yielded comprehensive results, with 22 observed factors being reasonably allocated and meeting the necessary conditions, categorized into 6 primary factor groups: information content, entertainment, credibility, interactivity, Promotion, and Usefulness. However, during the multivariate regression phase, "information content" and "credibility" were

eliminated after two runs due to not meeting the condition $\text{Sig.} < 0.005$. The author also reconfirmed that only 4 hypotheses were appropriate and 2 hypotheses were eliminated.

The Usefulness factor achieved the highest standardized Beta coefficient of 0.387, equivalent to 38.7% influence on the purchase intention of young Facebook users after watching short advertisement videos. This finding is crucial as it underscores the necessity of providing useful content through short videos on Facebook, which helps motivate viewers to make purchases. Furthermore, the Promotion factor obtained a Beta coefficient of 0.213, accounting for 21.3% influence on the purchase intention on Facebook. This indicates the alignment with current advertising campaigns that often focus on promoting immediate purchase actions from ad content to capitalize on social media advertising time. The Entertainment factor ranked third with an influence of 17.9% on the intention to purchase among young users. This is significant because entertainment enhances the attractiveness of ad content, thereby generating interest from viewers.

Although the Interactivity factor only accounted for 14.9% of the influence, it is essential due to the role of interaction after watching videos on social media, through creating comments, 'like' or 'share' effects, facilitating companies to create more creative and focused content.

7. MANAGEMENT IMPLICATIONS

Based on the discussion above, we can conclude that Usefulness is the most important factor in creating short advertising videos to increase users' purchase intention. To achieve this, businesses need to implement advertising campaigns with short, concise videos that highlight the product's key features and the real-life benefits it brings to consumers, as well as the advantages of the brand. For example, using a messaging system to quickly respond to customer inquiries and integrating direct purchase links in advertising videos can stimulate consumer interest and purchase intention, as they can complete the purchase process conveniently and quickly. The research by Almarashdeh et al., (2019) has also demonstrated a positive correlation between Usefulness and consumers' purchase intention, supporting this viewpoint.

To encourage consumption and boost sales, businesses need to create attractive incentive policies such as discounts during major holidays or volume-based price reductions. Such discounts can stimulate consumers' purchase intention, prompting them to buy more to take advantage of the discounted offer. Companies using short advertising videos should focus on attractive incentive policies, promotion programs, and accompanying products to attract potential customers. This aligns with the previous study by Hongdiyanto et al., (2020) which highlighted consumers' expectations regarding price and quality in advertising incentive programs. However, the implementation of discount incentive policies needs to be carefully considered to avoid impacting the company's profitability. In addition to focusing on incentive policies, companies should ensure that their products and services meet customer requirements and desires for quality and price,

helping to maintain not only attractiveness but also customer trust, contributing to the long-term success of marketing and sales strategies.

Regarding the entertainment factor, according to Teixeira and Stipp (2013), the entertainment aspect in advertising includes elements such as engaging content, creativity, stimulating adventures, and arousing consumer curiosity. To ensure balance and harmony in advertising, content producers need to carefully consider the distribution between product and service advertising content and entertainment elements. The duration of video advertising also needs to be adjusted appropriately to avoid causing discomfort for viewers and eliciting unwanted reactions, such as dissatisfaction with the brand's advertising.

Finally, in terms of the interactive factor, Prakash et al., (2019) suggest that interaction through advertising has the potential to generate a more positive attitude from customers and significantly influence purchase intention through advertising. Therefore, businesses need to invest in producing short videos containing engaging, useful content with the ability to create debate and discussion, thereby attracting attention and encouraging consumers to spend more time learning about the advertising and gaining a deeper understanding of the product and brand. As a result, consumers' attitudes can shift from indifference to curiosity and purchase intention.

The above are some implications for businesses based on the data analysis results and collection. However, there are certain limitations to the study:

- Firstly, the use of a sample in this study was limited to young people in a university, so expanding the age range for further research could provide clearer and more comprehensive insights into the impact of advertising on consumers.
- Secondly, referencing additional factors could help diversify the model and create new unique findings, adding value to the research. In this way, the proposed management implications can become richer and have broader practical applications.

References

- 1) Almarashdeh, I., Jaradat, G., Abuhamdah, A., Alsmadi, M., Alazzam, M. B., Alkhasawneh, R., & Awawdeh, I. (2019). The Difference between Shopping Online Using Mobile Apps and Website Shopping: A Case Study of Service Convenience. *International Journal of Computer Information Systems and Industrial Management Applications*. 11(1), 151-160.
- 2) Athapaththu, J. C., & Kulathunga, K. M. S. D. (2018). Factors affecting online purchase intention: A study of Sri Lankan Online Customers, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology research*, (7) 9,120-128
- 3) Donmez, N. (2022). Impact of Video Marketing on Consumer Purchase Intention. *LIGS University*. Retrieved from: [Https://Ligsuniversity.Com](https://Ligsuniversity.Com)
- 4) Donni, R., Dastane, O., Haba, H. F., & Selvaraj, K. (2018). Consumer perception factors for fashion M-commerce and its impact on loyalty among working adults. *Business and Economic Research*, 8(2), 168-192. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.5296/ber.v8i2.13044>

- 5) Han, (2022). Research on Short Video Marketing Model in the New Media Era. *International Conference on Comprehensive Art and Cultural Communication (CACC 2022)*: 195-198.
- 6) Hongdiyanto, C., Hartono, W., Ongkowijoyo, G., & Saputra, V. (2020). The Effect of Discount and Promotion towards Customer Purchase Intention in Online Shop. *Journal of Wellbeing Management and Applied Psychology*. 3(3), 21-30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13106/jwmap.2020.Vol3.no3.21>
- 7) Hu TAO, Jing-hui YANG. On the marketing model of short video [J]. *China market*, 2018 (32): 119 – 121.
- 8) Kurdi, B., Alshurideh, M., Akour, I., Tariq, E., AlHamad, A., & Alzoubi, H. (2022). The effect of social media influencers' characteristics on consumer intention and attitude toward Keto products purchase intention. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 6(4), 1135-1146.
- 9) Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: How message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on social media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58-73.
- 10) Martins, J., Costa, C., Oliveira, T., Goncalves, R., & Branco, F. (2019). How smartphone advertising influences consumers' purchase intention. *Journal of Business Research*. 94(C), 378-387.
- 11) NGO, T. T. A., LE, T. M. T., NGUYEN, T. H., LE, T. G., NGO, G. T., & NGUYEN, T. D. (2022). The Impact of SNS Advertisements on Online Purchase Intention of Generation Z: An Empirical Study of TikTok in Vietnam. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 9(5), 497–506.
- 12) Rajan, P., Lyn, F., Mun, N., Sian, K., & Yi, L. (2021). Facebook advertising and online purchasing decisions: an analysis of the uses and gratifications theory. *Advanced International Journal of Business, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (AIJBES)*, 3(7), 10-23.
- 13) Seo, Eun-Ju & Park, Jin-Woo. (2018). A study on the effects of social media marketing activities on brand equity and customer response in the airline industry. *Journal of Air Transport Management*. 66(1), 36-41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2017.09.014>
- 14) Skjuve, M., & Brandtzaeg, P. B. (2019). Facebook live: A mixed-methods approach to explore individual live streaming practices and motivations on Facebook. *Interacting with Computers*, 31(3), 589-602.
- 15) Suharyanto, A., Hidayat, T. W. (2018). Revealing Medan's Chinese Ethnic Identity in Advertising Grief at Harian Analisa Newspaper. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal) Humanities and Social Sciences*. 1(4), 83-92. DOI:10.33258/birci.v1i4.96
- 16) Teixeira, T. S., & Stipp, H. (2013). Optimizing the Amount of Entertainment in Advertising: What's So Funny about Tracking Reactions to Humor? *Journal of Advertising Research*. 53(3), 286-296. DOI: 10.2501/JAR-53-3-286-296.
- 17) Tran, V. D. (2020). The relationship among product risk, perceived satisfaction and purchase intentions for online shopping. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(6), 221-231.
- 18) Voorveld, H. A. (2019). Brand communication in social media: A research agenda. *Journal of Advertising*, 48 (1), 14–26.
- 19) Wen-sheng, SHAN and Lei LI. Short-term video marketing strategy and value research in the era of mobile internet. *Journal of Changsha University*.2015 29(4):35-37.